

**ACADEMIC STAFF USES OF INTERNET, INFORMATION NEEDS AND
INFORMATION-SEEKING BEHAVIOUR AMONG ACADEMIC STAFF IN FEDERAL
UNIVERSITIES IN SOUTH-SOUTH, NIGERIA**

BY

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to determine academic staff uses of internet, information needs and Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff in Federal University in South-South, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study two null hypotheses were generated to direct the study. Literature review was done according to the variables under study. A survey research design was adopted for the study. This design was considered appropriate because it allows the researcher to make inferences and generalizations about the population by selecting and studying the sample for the study. A sample of three thousand, five hundred (3500) respondents was randomly selected for the study. The selection was done through the stratified random sampling technique. The questionnaire was the main instrument used for data collection. The instrument was subjected to face validation by one expert from Environmental Education and two experts in measurement and evaluation in the Faculty of Education, University of Calabar. The reliability estimate of the instrument was established through the Cronbach alpha reliability method. Regression analysis was the statistical analysis technique adopted to test the hypotheses under study. This statistical tool was used because of the nature of the variables involved in the study. All hypotheses were subjected to testing at a .05 level of significance with relative degrees of freedom. The results of the analysis revealed that uses of the internet, and social media to access information needs significantly relate to Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff. Based on the findings of the study it was recommended among others that academic staff of the Federal Universities should patronize the library while utilizing the existing and alternative sources of information.

INTRODUCTION

The increasingly widespread use of social network sites to expand and deepen one's social connections is a relatively new but potentially important phenomenon that has implications for teaching, learning, and information-seeking behavior in the 21st century. This work is necessary to fill in gaps in knowledge toward adopting social network sites in teaching, learning, and information seeking process in formal sites that can be efficiently applied in the educational

system and provides direction for subsequent researches and as a guideline for future research in social network sites in education.

Several studies mentioned that libraries need to emphasize the planning of user-oriented programs to provide more responsive and accountable service (Osiobe, 1998; Owolabi, Jimoh & Okpeh, 2010, as cited in Akuma & Iqbal, 2012). Based on these previous studies, it is necessary for libraries to have the knowledge and need to understand the user group to be served. Information needs depend on the discipline of study and level, for example, undergraduate and postgraduate students. There is a barrier to accessing information when users are unaware or lack awareness of resources and services provided by the library. The users also need to know using library resources and services so that they can use information access tools efficiently.

Ironically, people generally do not perceive their social networking site as a source of information, but as a means to network, keep in touch with friends and keep abreast of happenings in their friends' lives. However, other researchers have found that breaking local, national, and international news is an important type of information that Facebook users share and take note of (e.g., Khoo, Fang, Tian, Xu & Wu, under preparation).

The above studies raise more curiosity on the seeking behavior of Academic staff of Federal University. With the upgrading of the university library system, there is no existing information on how these innovations have contributed to the accessibility and availability of educational materials and provoke passion to seek information.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Academic staff uses Internet and social media access to seek information

Studies of information seeking in a wide range of contexts have consistently found that human sources are the most preferred type of information source, that is, they are likely to be consulted first and are most frequently used (e.g., Savolainen & Kari, 2004). Case (2012) noted that the Use of other [information] channels tends to be related withed by the social presence they offer, that is, how much they are perceived as being like a face-to-face conversation with another person, or as Johnson puts it “the extent to which they reveal the presence of other human interactants and can capture the human, feeling side of relationships” (Johnson, 1997, p. 92). (Case, 2012, p. 153-155). This suggests that social media sites may become preferred sources of information, as they offer some amount of social presence, and some applications convey the immediacy of face-to-face conversation.

Types of Information Seeking Behaviour on Social Media

Compared to other online information sources, social media sites appear to favor the following types of information-seeking behavior:

- everyday life information behavior, for non-work and non-school information needs
- browsing, monitoring, and asking, rather than searching
- opportunistic information acquisition, including serendipitous information encountering and environmental awareness, rather than purposive information seeking
- information publishing, giving, and sharing, as much as information seeking

- intermediary roles are undertaken by users voluntarily, including information seeking by proxy, information summarizing, and information forwarding
- social information behavior and development of information communities
- information use and evaluation. An interesting subtype of information-sharing behavior that is gaining the attention of researchers is information forwarding, including reposting and re-tweeting, and propagation of information in online social networks (e.g., Kim, 2014; Sutton, Spiro, Johnson, Fitzhugh,

Information needs and information seeking behavior of academic staff of the University

Some studies of information behavior on social media have found that users exhibit multiple types of information behavior, which seem to complement and even interact with one another. In particular, researchers have noted that the following types of information behavior are complementary and related:

1. information in everyday life and work/school contexts
2. searching (the Web) and asking (the individual's social network)
3. informational and socio-emotional support
4. strong and weak ties
5. searching, browsing, monitoring, and awareness
6. multiple types of information sources.

Savolainen (1995) noted that everyday life and work were sometimes inseparable. In a study of undergraduates' everyday life information seeking at a Canadian university, Given (2002) found their everyday and academic lives to be inextricably tied. Similarly, Kari and Hartel (2007) found that work was after all the most central part of everyday life. The question then is how work (or school) tasks/needs/information seeking are different from non-work ones, and how they affect each other. Certainly work and non-work information behavior encroach on each other's expected time and space.

At least two studies have found that searching (the Web) and asking (the individual's social network) are complementary behavior when information is needed for important decisions. Searching is used to identify detailed information and the range of options. An individual's social network is then consulted to evaluate the information sources and interpret and confirm the information. In a small study involving 12 participants, Morris, Teevan, and Panovich (2010) found that asking provided valuable feedback and confirmation of results found using a search engine. They provided some quotations from the participants to illustrate their attitude: In a large-scale survey of university students on 25 campuses, Head and Eisenberg (2011) found that, in addition to seeking information from human sources, 83% of their respondents consulted friends/family to help evaluate information sources for personal use. They found that many searches involved decision-making to resolve problems with real-life consequences and the searches may go on for days. Interviews with students suggested that "when students perceive the consequences to be greater, they are more apt to go offline to double-check the quality of information they have found with a human-mediated source or sources."

Information provided on social media sites tends to be accompanied by socio-emotional support. Wikgren (2003) studied the information behavior of participants in a health and lifestyle

discussion forum. She found that emotional support and information sharing were closely linked activities: Communicating health information in virtual communities is, on the one hand, an exchange of facts and communication of scientific knowledge, but, on the other hand, a communication of meaning and socio-emotional support, and perhaps even a "construction of mastery." (Wikgren, 2003, p. 238) Godbold (2013) showed that informational and emotional support is inextricably intertwined and that expressions of emotion, in fact, support communication of information and adds to the information. She noted that "emotional cues are an intrinsic element in the informational processes observed." Emotional support is sometimes expressed indirectly by the "tone" of the language and can have a cumulative effect through consensus in tone and echoing of vocabulary over a sequence of posts. Emotional tones are used to select and reinforce particular perspectives, and to modify understanding of information. Examples of tones that Gobold gave include humorous/playful, worried, confident, unconcerned, reassuring, cheerful, bemused, and fascinated tone.

Social media sites exhibit both strong and weak ties, and weak ties can become stronger over time as users continue to interact online or when they decide to meet offline as well. Granovetter (1973) proposed the theory of weak ties that distant and infrequent relationships are efficient for knowledge sharing and giving access to new information by bridging disconnected groups and individuals, in contrast to strong ties between family, friends, and colleagues. A study by Goecks and Mynatt (2004) found that there was a strong difference in the sharing of information between strong and weak tie relationships. Information shared with a strong tie group tends to stay within the group whereas information shared with a weak tie is usually shared outside a group and tends to get disseminated further compared to strong ties. This suggests that different types of information are shared via different types of relationships and with different categories

of friends. This merits further investigation. Furthermore, relationships can evolve from weak ties to stronger ties over time, with corresponding changes in the types of information shared.

People can be expected to consult different types of information sources when the topic is important to them. Search engines make this easier as their search results typically include a range of sources. Head and Eisenberg (2011) found that some people specifically looked for certain information sources, including blogs, government sites, and Wikipedia. How the different types of information sources (including social media sources) complement and interact with one another, and how users evaluate them, has not been much studied. It is probably more productive to study information seeking in social media sites within a broader context that includes information seeking on the Web as well as offline personal information seeking.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for the study is the survey design. According to Isangedighi, Joshua, Asim, and Ekuri (2004), survey research design involves the collection of data to accurately and objectively describe existing phenomena. Studies that make use of this approach are employed to obtain a picture of the present condition of particular phenomena. Survey research is therefore very useful for opinion and attitudes studies. It depends basically on the questionnaire and interviews as means of data collection.

The survey research design is economic in the sense that a study is representing samples that permits inference from the generalization of the population that could be expensive to study as a whole.

The Area of the study is south-south zone of Nigeria. The rationale for the adoption of these zones includes administrative convenience, a decrease in fear of marginalization of a minority group, and protection of the interest as well as the privileges of the minority groups. The zone has a high literacy rate with several private and government-owned Universities and public libraries. Some of the libraries are fully digital like the E-library in Akwa Ibom and other states in the region... Other states in the zone with Federal University Libraries which is the focus of this study include Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, and Rivers. The region is often referred to as the Niger Delta with a high deposit of mineral resources.

The study population is taken from the Academic staff in Federal Universities in South-South Zone. The estimated number of Academic staff in selected Universities was 9754. The sampling technique adopted for the study is the simple random sampling technique. The sample for the study is made up of 3500 respondents randomly drawn from all the University Library division

of the research area. The main instrument used for data collection was Social Media and Information behaviour questionnaire (SMAISBQ) designed by the researcher. Two kinds of validity were established for the instrument of the study, these were the face and content validity. Face validity refers to the way the questionnaire terms appear to take care of relevant content in the subject area of interest while content validity refers to the extent to which the instrument represents or samples the content to be measured. The face and content validity were established by using the experts in the measurement and evaluation field in the faculty of education and the supervisor and experts certified that the instrument was face and content valid and could be used for the study. To determine the reliability of the instrument (questionnaire), a trial test was carried out using 50 subjects selected from a school in the study area that is not part of the sample. The copies of the instruments distributed were analyzed using the Cronbach alpha reliability method to obtain and estimate the internal consistency of the instrument. The result of the reliability ranges from 0.70 to 0.82.

Presentation of result

In this section, each hypothesis is re-stated, and the result of data analysis carried out to test it is presented. Each hypothesis of the study was tested at a .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant relationship between the use of the internet and social media and Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff

The independent variable in this hypothesis is the use of the internet and social media to access; while the dependent variable is the Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff.

Simple regression analysis was employed to test this hypothesis. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Simple regression result of the relationship between Uses of the Internet and social media to access and Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff

Model	R	R. square	Adjusted R. square	The std error of the estimate	
1	.927(a)	.859	.859	1.17986	
Model	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	p-value
Regression	3667.684	1	3667.684	21323.744*	.066(a)
Residual	602.762	3498	0.172		
Total	4270.446	3499			

* Significant at .05 level.

The simple regression analysis of the relationship between Uses of the Internet and social media to access the Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff yielded a coefficient of multiple regression (R) of .927 and a multiple regression R-square (R^2) of .859 and an adjusted R^2 of .859. The adjusted R^2 of .859 indicated that the use of the internet and social media to access accounted for 85.9% of the determinant Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff in the study area. This finding is a critical indication that Uses of the internet and social media to access is relatively high in the area of the study. The F-value of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) obtained from the regression table was $F = 21323.744$ and the sig. value of .000 (or $p < .05$) at the degree of freedom (df) 1 and 3499. This result implies that Uses of the internet and social media access is a significant predictor of the Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff.

Hypothesis two

Information needs do not significantly relate with Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff.

The independent variable in this hypothesis is information needs; while the dependent variable is Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff. Simple regression analysis was employed to test this hypothesis. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Simple regression result of the relationship between information needs and Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff

Model	R	R. square	Adjusted R. square	The std error of the estimate	
1	.452(a)	.204	.202	2.80152	
Model	Sum of square	df	Mean square	F	p-value
Regression	872.031	1	872.031	897.151*	.000(a)
Residual	3398.415	3498	0.972		
Total	4270.446	3499			

* Significant at .05 level.

The simple regression analysis of the relationship between information needs on the Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff yielded a coefficient of multiple regression (R) of .452 and a multiple regression R-square (R^2) of .204 and an adjusted R^2 of .202. The adjusted R^2 of .202 indicated that the information needs accounted for 28.6% of the determinant Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff in the study area. This finding is a critical indication that information needs are relatively high in the area of the study. The F-value of the

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) obtained from the regression table was $F = 897.151$ and the sig. value of .000 (or $p < .05$) at the degree of freedom (df) 1 and 3499. This result implies that information needs are a significant predictor of Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the first hypothesis showed that the use of the internet and social media to access has a significant relationship with the Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff. The finding of this hypothesis is in line with the study of Case (2012) who noted that the Use of other [information] channels tends to be related withed by the social presence they offer, that is, how much they are perceived as being like a face-to-face conversation with another person, or as Johnson puts it “the extent to which they reveal the presence of other human interactants and can capture the human, feeling side of relationships. This suggests that social media sites may become preferred sources of information, as they offer some amount of social presence, and some applications convey the immediacy of face-to-face conversation.

The result of the second hypothesis revealed that information needs have a significant relationship with Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff. The finding of this hypothesis is in line with the view of Kari and Hartel (2007) who found that work was after all the most central part of everyday life. The question then is how work (or school) tasks/needs/information seeking are different from non-work ones, and how they affect each other. Certainly work and non-work information behavior encroach on each other’s expected time and space.

Morris, Teevan, and Panovich (2010) also found that asking provided valuable feedback and confirmation of results found using a search engine. They provided some quotations from the participants to illustrate their attitude: In a large-scale survey of university students on 25 campuses. Head and Eisenberg (2011) also found that, in addition to seeking information from human sources, 83% of their respondents consulted friends/family to help evaluate information sources for personal use. They found that many searches involved decision-making to resolve problems with real-life consequences and the searches may go on for days. Interviews with students suggested that "when students perceive the consequences to be greater, they are more apt to go offline to double-check the quality of information they have found with a human-mediated source or sources." Information provided on social media sites tends to be accompanied by socio-emotional support. Emotional support and information sharing were closely linked activities: Communicating health information in virtual communities is, on the one hand, an exchange of facts and a communication of scientific knowledge, but, on the other hand, a communication of meaning and socio-emotional support, and perhaps even a "construction of mastery."

Godbold (2013) also showed that informational and emotional support is inextricably intertwined and that expressions of emotion support the communication of information and add to the information. She noted that "emotional cues are an intrinsic element in the informational processes observed." Emotional support is sometimes expressed indirectly by the "tone" of the language and can have a cumulative effect through consensus in tone and echoing of vocabulary over a sequence of posts. Emotional tones are used to select and reinforce particular perspectives, and to modify understanding of information. Examples of tones that Gobold gave include humorous/playful, worried, confident, unconcerned, reassuring, cheerful, bemused, and

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People can be expected to consult different types of information sources when the topic is important to them. Search engines make this easier as their search results typically include a range of sources. Some people specifically looked for certain information sources, including blogs, government sites, and Wikipedia. How the different types of information sources (including social media sources) complement and interact with one another, and how users evaluate them, has not been much studied. It is probably more productive to study information seeking in social media sites within a broader context that includes information seeking on the Web as well as offline impersonal information seeking.

Conclusion/ Recommendations

Based on the results and findings of the study, the following conclusions were reached. Uses of the internet, and social media to access information needs significantly relate with Information Seeking Behaviour of Academic Staff.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Internet service providers such as MTN, GLO, Airtel, and 9mobile should ensure steady and affordable Internet services to enable easy access to online information.

2. Phone manufacturers should include more software features (language editing software) that will enable proper writing and editing of downloaded documents that are offline and not data-consuming.
3. Relevant and current books should be acquired and stored in the library to make it the first point of contact when searching for information.
4. Library environment should be conducive enough to enhance high patronage by library users
5. Information should be readily available and easily accessed by library users
6. Bottlenecks experienced in accessing information in the library should be removed to encourage patronage of the Library
7. Academic staff of Federal Universities should update their knowledge on how to use social media.
8. Staff should be advised to use an Android phone to enable them to do research through the internet and social media to share online resources.
9. Information-seeking behavior among academic staff of Federal Universities should be sustained.

5.4 Suggestions for further studies

Based on the limitations of the study, the following suggestions were made for further studies:

- i. A replication of the study should be carried out again covering the institutions under study to ascertain the validity and reliability of the present study.
- ii. A similar study should be carried out on the factors that are not incorporated in the present study.

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